

Updated distribution of *Dilophus clavicornus* Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996 (Diptera: Bibionidae), with new records from Romania, Montenegro and France

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Abstract: *Dilophus clavicornus* Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996 (Diptera: Bibionidae: Bibioninae) is reported for the first time from Romania, Montenegro and France. Photos of male habitus, fore tibia and male terminalia are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, Europe, Insecta, March flies

Introduction

The family Bibionidae includes approximately 700 extant species across eight genera (Fitzgerald, 2009). In Europe, 45–50 species have been documented (Skartveit 2004), belonging to four genera: *Bibio* Geoffroy, *Dilophus* Meigen, *Hesperinus* Walker, and *Penthetria* Meigen. However, the level of faunistic knowledge varies by country; for example, it is well-documented in France with 24 recorded species, moderately studied in Romania with 18 species, and with just two species recorded in Montenegro. For recent studies on the Romanian fauna, see Iacob (1980), Papp (2010) and Pintilioaie & Kolcsár (2022). On the Montenegro fauna see Duda (1930), Papp (2010) and Krivosheina (2022). For accounts on the French fauna, refer to Haenni (1994), Haenni & Quintin (2012) and Haenni et al. (2023).

Dilophus clavicornus Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996 (Fig. 1), originally described from Israel and surrounding regions, was only recently reported in Europe from northern Greece (Haenni & Ramel, 2017). Its distribution in southern Europe is evidently broader, as it is now recorded from three additional countries: Romania, Montenegro, and France.

Material and methods

The Romanian specimens, collected by A.-M. Pintilioaie (AMP), are preserved in ethanol. The French specimens, collected by J.-P. Haenni (JPH) and J.-J. Porteneuve (JJP), are dry-preserved (micro-pinned). All these specimens are housed in the collection of the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle de Neuchâtel (MHNN), Switzerland. Additionally, micropinned material from Montenegro was exam-

Fig. 1. Habitus of *Dilophus clavicornus* Skartveit & Kaplan, 2016, male (France: Millau); (scale bar 2.0 mm).

ined from the collection of the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle de Genève (MHNG), Switzerland. All identifications were conducted by the first author (JPH). Morphological terminology follows Fitzgerald (2004). The geographic distribution map was created using the SimpleMapp tool.

Results

Dilophus clavicornus Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996

Type locality: Israel, Tel Aviv District, Herzliya.

References: Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996: 82 (original description); Skartveit & Willassen, 1996: 2 (phylogeny); Haenni & Ramel, 2017: 40 (new record).

Material examined. ROMANIA. Constanța County, Agigea, “Dunele Marine de la Agigea” Nature Reserve, 44.086721°N, 28.641793°E, 12 m a.s.l., 14 October 2022, 3 ♂♂, A.-M. Pintilioaie leg., MHNN. FRANCE. Aude: Salsigne, 43.332415°N,

2.350520°E, 330 m, 20–22 October 1981, 26 ♂♂, J.-P. Haenni leg.; Lastours, Les-Quatre-Châteaux, 43.331777°N, 2.378234°E, 300 m, 19 October 1981, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, J.-P. Haenni leg.; Aveyron, Millau, 44.104657°N, 3.071705°E, 388 m, 5–10 October 2024, 14 ♂♂, J.-P. Haenni leg.; Hérault, Saint-Gély-du-Fesc, 43.690282°N, 3.804853°E, 106 m, 18 October 1987, 5 ♂♂, J.-P. Haenni leg.; Lunel-Viel, 43.6721317°N, 4.0900444°E, 28 m, 24 October 2016, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, J.-J. Porteneuve leg.; all housed in MHNN. GREECE. Sérres, Neo Petritsi, 420 m, 20–26 October 2008, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, G. Ramel leg., MHNN (recorded by Haenni & Ramel, 2017). MONTENEGRO. Lovcen, Krstac, 900–1000 m, 18 October 1982, 2 ♂♂, P. Lauterer leg., MHNG; Đjuraševići – Plavi Horizont, 20–100 m, 22 October 1982, 6 ♂♂, P. Lauterer leg., MHNG/MHNN; Radovići, 70–100 m, 25 October 1982, 9 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, P. Lauterer leg., MHNG/MHNN.

Distribution. *Dilophus clavicornus* has been recorded from Israel/Palestine, including the Central, Haifa, Jerusalem, Northern and Tel Aviv Districts, as well as the West Bank/Judea and Samaria Area

Fig. 2. Details of *Dilophus clavicornus* Skartveit & Kaplan, 2016. A. Left anterior leg, inner view (scale bar 0.5 mm); B. Male terminalia, dorsal view (scale bar 0.1 mm).

(Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996). It was later documented in Greece (Haenni & Ramel, 2014). New records are reported for Romania (Agigea), Montenegro, and France (Aude, Aveyron, Hérault). In France, the presence of *D. clavicornus* had been known for years by the first author but was not formally published until now. Additionally, two probable records, based on photographs only, are available from the citizen science forum Le Monde des Insectes (2025), originating from the departments of Charente-Maritime and Vendée (Atlantic coast); however, these specimens have not been examined.

Phenology and ecology. *Dilophus clavicornus* appears to be a strictly autumnal species, with its flight period limited to October in Europe and extending to November–December in Israel (Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996). In Agigea (Romania) and Millau (France), specimens were observed swarming at 1–2 metres above the ground during daytime. In contrast, most specimens from Salsignes (France) were collected on flowers, particularly *Hedera helix* L. and *Seseli* sp. L.

Taxonomic note. *Dilophus clavicornus* and *Dilophus bispinosus* Lundström, 1913 are closely related species, best distinguished by the arrangement of spines on the anterior tibiae. In *D. clavicornus*, there are three spines arranged in an oblique row basally, with one isolated spine apically (Fig. 2A). In contrast, *D. bispinosus* has two rows of two spines, with the spines of the apical row more widely spaced than those of the basal row. The male genitalia of both species are very similar (Skartveit & Kaplan, 2016: Figs 23–24); the male genitalia of *D. clavicornus* can be seen in Fig. 2B. In females, *Dilophus clavicornus* is darker in colour, with rufous-yellowish markings confined to the humeral calli, sides of the notum, femora, and abdomen. In contrast, *Dilophus bispinosus* has a predominantly yellow body and legs. It is likely that *D. clavicornus* was confused with *D. bispinosus* in the original description of the species by Lundström (1913). This is evident from the three female specimens from Lesina [= Hvar, Croatia] mentioned by Lundström, which likely belong to *D. clavicornus* based on the characteristics described by the

Fig. 3. The current distribution of *Dilophus clavicornis* Skartveit & Kaplan, 2016 (red circles – published records; yellow circles – new records).

author: “larger and darker [than specimens of *D. bispinosus* from Hungary], notum partly brown-black, mid and hind legs rufous-brown” [“Rückenschild teilweise schwarzbraun; mittleren und hintersten Beine braunrot; grösser und dunkler”]. Unfortunately, this material was destroyed in the 1956 fire at the National Hungarian Natural History Museum in Budapest.

Discussion

Dilophus clavicornis is more widely distributed than previously thought (Fig. 3), likely exhibiting a Mediterranean-type distribution. The earliest European records presented here date back to the early 1980s (France: 1981, Montenegro: 1982), well before the recognition of its specific status and its formal description from Israel (Skartveit & Kaplan, 1996). All these early records are located within the true Mediterranean region. However, findings from Agigea (Romania) and Millau (France), as well as the two unverified records from the Atlantic coast of France, suggest that the species may have expanded its range beyond the Mediterranean region in recent years. Further records will be necessary to address this question.

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Authors’ contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Jean-Paul Haenni: conceptualisation, data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Alexandru-Mihai Pintilioaie: conceptualisation, data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Daniel de Castro Schelesky-Prado: conceptualisation, data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Jean-Jacques Porteneuve: data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

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